
Transformational Leadership Effects on Organizational Performance through Mediating Effects from Organizational Innovation: A Case Study of Public Commercial Banks in Bangladesh

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Abstract

In dynamic environment, preferential organizational performance demands proper guidance and capacity to address organizational changes and to absorb the market challenges. Therefore, the presence of effective leadership practices and encouragement in organizational innovativeness is imperative because some organization fails to achieve their desired goal due to lack of employee motivation and their limited understating of their relationship in strategic issues. With this study, we investigate the nexus between transformational leadership, organizational innovativeness and organizational performance of the bank-based financial institutions in Bangladesh. We test the model with a sample of 350 respondents by applying structural equation modeling (SEM). The study findings unveiled (1) Transformational leadership positively influence on organizational performance through organizational innovation. It is implying that organizational leaders who adapted transformational leadership style in their organization contribute positively in enhancing operating performance: (2) Transformational leadership positively induces organizational innovation. (3) Study findings further suggest positive interaction between organizational innovations to organizational performance, this relationship signifies that organization could achieve market competitiveness with innovative products and services offering over the competitors eventually accelerate organizational performance.

Keywords: Transformational leadership; Organizational Innovation, Organizational performance; Public commercial banks; Bangladesh

Highlights of the study:

1. First ever-empirical investigation explaining the transformational leadership effects on performance of public commercial banks in Bangladesh.
2. Transformational leadership positively associated with organizational performance
3. Organizational innovation positively influenced by transformational leadership

I. Introduction

Over the past three decades, considerable work had been performed by researchers of explaining the leadership effects on organizational performance, creativity, and innovativeness either in direct or/and indirect ways (Zhu et al., 2013). Organizational performance is not only the output of simply investment in long-term assets and recruitment of skilled employees but also established good connectivity among all the factors available in the organization. Operational efficiency demands a healthy ambiance in the organization, positive attitudes of employees about the organization, efficient transaction in workload and a participative management for acknowledging employees efforts and contribution (Ismail Al-Alawi et al., 2007; Sivadas and Dwyer, 2000; Petrou et al., 2018; Appelbaum et al., 2018; Aguenza and Som, 2018; Adjibolosoo, 2018). Therefore, maintaining a stable organizational performance over time it is imperative to address employee's behavior, improvement in organizational process, and manager's

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attitudes. In a study, Muehlheusser et al. (2018) explained in their study that managers in the organization with professional attitudes can have immense power to motivate employees towards achieving a targeted organizational goal than managers having no professionalisms. Therefore, it is said that the perception hold by leaders in the organization stimulates organizational performance and encourage the employee to think out of the box by playing an informative and transformational role in the organization.

Transformational leadership, according to Bass and Avolio (1990) and Avolio et al. (1999), is such an intrinsic quality of leaders with charismatic and stimulating power to encourage employees with an individualistic aspect. Transformational leadership can be defined as a leadership style that encourages, enlightened employees to understand the importance of collectivism and assists them in achieving common goal rather reacting to individual approach. Theories evolving, in human resources management, transformation leadership emphasized on emotion, values, and the necessity of leadership orientation in encouraging innovativeness of employees. Since, work force is one of the key element in organizational development and understanding their importance leaders initiate professional development tasks for employee capacity development (Avolio and Bass, 1995; Bass and Avolio, 1990; García-Morales et al., 2008; Garcia-Morales et al., 2008). Furthermore, Transformational leadership stimulates organizational performance by influencing fundamental attitudes, assumptions of individuals who are directly involving organization, and creating a common goal for all. Transformational leadership styles produce more conducive organizational environment than transactional leadership style, which eventually promotes organizational performance and innovativeness.

Transformational leadership inspires followers to higher value proposition, established emotional linkage with organizational goal, and commitment to achieve results as a part of organization's member. Effective leadership practices in the organization treated as a motivational factor for the employees that guided towards achieving the targeted goal for the organization (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995; Morecroft et al., 1994). It is because of managers and employees perceptions about organizations and organizational culture strongly guided by organizational leadership style (Fowler and O'Gorman, 2005). The role of effective leadership is critical for the transformation of mission and vision of the organization along with the establishment of effective commitment, strong motivation towards an organizational common goal. Furthermore, leadership style guided organization to achieve the targeted goal with effective and efficient coordination by confirming direction and controlling measures in the organization (Xu and Wang, 2008) Well-appreciated leadership style, according to Harris et al. (2007), is necessary of achieving substantial organizational development in a dynamic business environment.

Among all other leadership styles, transformational leadership grasped the apex position in enlightening the leadership styles effect on organizational performance. Transformational leadership style transforms the organizational environment in accordance with a focus to organizational issues and organizational needs. Therefore, further organizational improvements positively induced overall performance because the transformation process lies with the current demand and employee's expectation. Transformational leadership, According to Bass and Avolio (1994), established a bridge between followers precisely, employee and leaders through the formulation of organizational goal into a common goal. Transformational leadership style allows employees innovativeness by creating new opportunities, encourage looking beyond their self-interest and acknowledging their contribution to organizational development. Wang et al (2011) found a positive linkage between transformational leadership and individual employee's performance improvement, furthermore, they also explained that the effect of transformational leadership also evident in the different level of management. The followers of transformational leadership style are associated with a satisfying and self-driving relationship with the group.

The effects from transformational leadership on organizational performance observed in empirical studies through various intermediate contracts such as, culture (Ogbonna and Harris, 2000), learning (García-Morales et al., 2012), innovation (Arif and Akram, 2018), entrepreneurship development, knowledge management (Gowen et al., 2009) and human resources development (Zhu et al., 2013).

However, understanding the mediating effect role of different variables in transformational leadership and organizational performance it is still yet to establish conclusive evidence regarding any particular factors that can have prominent role as mediating position in this regards. This study seeks to unveil the role of transformational leadership on organizational performance through the mediating influence of organizational innovation.

Organizational innovation, there are numerous definition available in empirical literatures, for this study we define organizational innovation in terms of product development, process improvement, and management association. The act of product line development with offering new produce and process which includes concept or idea development and transform into final form (Belliveau et al.). The remaining structure, apart from section I dealing with introduction, of this article organized in the following ways. Section II represents relevant literatures focused on explaining the relationship between transformational leadership, organizational innovation, and organizational performance. Section III containing the details explanation of latent variables definition, data collection procedures, and hypothesized model for estimation. The detailed model estimation and discussion represents in Section IV. Finally, Section V exhibits the conclusion and further research prospects.

II. Literature review

2.1 Organizational innovation and operational performance

Empirical literatures focusing organizational behavior stressed the importance adaptive organizational innovativeness for creating congenial environment for motivating and cultivating employees skilled see, for an instant (Calantone et al., 2002; Tushman and Nadler, 1986) The more innovative products and services or methods offered by organization, the greater possibility of knowledge expansion, skills development, and eventually higher performance for organization. Organizational innovation, according to Cohen and Levinthal (1990), depends on the organizational knowledge base and learning process thus endorsed into the permanent knowledge base. From theoretical aspects, organizational innovation is imperative for promoting organizational performance. Marketing theories suggest that innovativeness in the organization accelerate pioneering ideas for product development, process improvement for achieving greater market share, which eventually offers a higher level of performance, at large. Adaptation of organizational innovation policy creates comparative advantages with a competitive edge, which is difficult to imitate by external competitors and thus allows the organization to excel its operational performance in the long-run (Lengnick-Hall, 1992; Lieberman and Montgomery, 1988).

The positive effect from organization innovation to organizational performance discussed by large number of researchers see, for an example (Fartash et al., 2018; García-Sánchez et al., 2018a; Yunis et al., 2018; Naranjo-Valencia et al., 2016; Azar and Ciabuschi, 2017; Soto-Acosta et al., 2016) . Organization innovation act as a prime catalyst in dynamic business environment, it is because, innovation not only introduced new ideas, knowledge, and process but also assist in improving individual employee's skills, capability and capacity to adapt in every business situation. Besides that, organizational innovation assists in overcoming business barrier offered by competitors with a competitive position.

Organizational innovation influenced by technological advancement because the progress of technological integration imperatively changes the process of organizational development. First mover advantages of adopting new technology produce greater flexibility and opportunity to avail complete position with organizational innovativeness (Giarratana and Torrissi, 2010)

Hypothesis₁: Organizational innovation positively influences on operational performance in the organization.

2.2 Transformational leadership and Organizational performance

Employees' attitude towards work and the organization immensely transformed by the perceived behavior from managers, more precisely the leader of any organization, which creates and shape employee mindset up. Therefore, in management literature, it is evident that a number of studies had already been performed focus to investigate the organizational leadership style effects on operational performance see, for example (Ogbonna and Harris, 2000; García-Morales et al., 2012; Avolio et al., 1999). The effects of leadership style on operational performance is multidimensional which is unveiled by researchers like, development to entrepreneurship quality, effective knowledge management (McFadden et al., 2009), human resource management (García-Morales et al., 2008), organizational capacity building (Rodríguez-Ponce, 2007). Leadership practices in an effective way in the organization increased employee's commitment toward their assigned responsibilities and targeted goal in the long-term. It is because the organization only focused on survival but also keen to attain a substantial improvement in their organizational performance as well. In order to reach ultimate organizational performance, it is inevitable to address market competitiveness, peruse continuous improvement strategies, and effective leadership style in the organization (Arslan and Staub, 2013). Therefore, sustainability in organizational performance from leadership style perspective extensively discussed in management literatures with positive note see, for example, (Subramony et al., 2018; Uhl-Bien and Arena, 2018; Barling et al., 2018; Bhargavi and Yaseen, 2016; Ogbonna and Harris, 2000; Peterson et al., 2003; Elenkov, 2002; Day and Lord, 1988). Effective leadership, therefore, style is an important source of management development that assists the organization to sustain organizational performance by stimulating effective allocation of resources in the organization so that employee can perform their designated jobs with comfort.

Leaders in the organization play critical roles that are acknowledged in literature as a catalyst to bring innovation, create a conducive environment for participatory management and enhance employee's capabilities and confidence. Furthermore, the leader's attributes and behavioral perception in the organization transform leadership effectiveness. Yukl, (2010), defined leadership as "the process of making others influenced and they should be able to understand to agree about what has to be done and how it should be done, and how to facilitate individuals and collective efforts to achieve the objectives you are working on". While Northouse (2018), gave another definition of leadership which states, "It is a process where a person encourages a group to reach a shared aim".

Leadership styles, precisely transformational leadership style foster a generalized definition of organizational goal and allow leaders in the organization to motivate and guide employees towards targeted goal with available resources by ensuring optimization. Transformational leadership transforms and creates new opportunities, challenges, and competitive position (Bass and Avolio, 1990) by promoting an ideal environment for the innovative team for performance, strong connection among employs and transmit strong motivation to innovation. In a study, Orabi (2016) observed transformational leadership positively influence the organizational performance of Banks performing in Jordan. In this study, he performed multiple regression analysis based on 213 sample data collected from different banks operating in Jordan.

Further evidence observed in Al Khajeh (2018) study. He performed investigation consideration six leadership style and their impact on organizational performance. Study findings revealed that transformation leadership, autocratic and democratic leadership style positively influence on organizational performance. In contrast, bureaucratic, charismatic and transactional leadership style adversely linked to organizational performance. Hoxha (2015) Performed another study by employing hierarchical regression, observed that the transformational leadership style transform employee's attitudes, and directly influence on organizational performance. Likewise, Trmal et al. (2015) performed structural equation model of addressing transformational leadership style impact on organizational performance. They conclude in their study that transformational leadership effectively promotes organizational development through transforming the individualistic approach to organizational common

goal. However, conflicting findings also available in existing empirical literature such as, in a study Koech and Namusonge (2012) found a negative association between transformational leadership and organizational performance at state corporation in Kenya. Based on empirical literatures evidence, we therefore assume that operational performance of bank-based financial institutions positively influenced by transformational leadership.

Hypothesis₂: Transformational leadership style positively linked with organizational performance.

2.3 Transformational leadership and organizational innovation

The nexus between leadership and organizational innovation tested in empirical studies and provide ample evidence by confirming their positive association see, for example (Makri and Scandura, 2010; Garcia-Morales et al., 2008; Oke et al., 2009; Strange and Mumford, 2002). In empirical studies, a range of leadership styles taken into consideration, however, transformational leadership attracts immense interest among researches of examining its influence on organizational innovation. Organizational innovation, according to Woodman et al. (1993), refers to advancement in the production process and innovative way to customer's service. Transformation into the innovation-oriented organization from traditional organizing process demands all level managers and employees effective and active participation in organizing, directing and effective control. Transformational leadership is based on motivational and empowerment which seeks to deliver continual and continuous changes among employees even in the organization (Jung et al., 2003).

The idea of transformational leadership first introduced by Burns (1978) and further development executed by Bass and Avolio (1995). According to them, transformational leadership has four key attributes charismatic role modeling, individualized consideration, inspirational motivation, and intellectual stimulation. Transformational leadership had a significant effect on individual creativity, while individual creativity had a significant effect on organizational innovation (Jung et al., 2008). In particular, the core factor that is responsible for transformational leadership to affect individual creativity is charisma, and the core factor that is responsible for emotional leadership to affect organizational innovation is self-management skills. Al-Omari and Hung (2012) Postulated that leadership enlightens employees' attitudes towards innovativeness and induced them to bring positive changes in the organization.

Transformational leadership became one of the key factors in fostering organizational innovation over the past decades through empowering of employs (Jung and Sosik, 2002) and offering innovative environment (Jung et al., 2003). A study was performed by Hsiao and Hsiao (2006) of investigating the role of organizational learning in transformational leadership and organizational innovation considering administrative personnel of education sector. Study findings unveiled that transformational leadership and organizational learning positively influence on organizational innovation. Further evidence can found in Gumusluoğlu and Ilsev (2009) study. They argued that transformational leadership practices in the organization act as motivational factor for enhancing organizational innovation. Again, Jung et al. (2003) observed a positive linkage between transformational leadership and organizational innovation in Taiwan companies.

A study conducted by Mokhber et al. (2015) with a sample of 220 managers from 100 Italian companies. Study finding suggests that organizational innovation can be accelerated with the effective adaption of transformational leadership style by the leaders. Oke et al. (2009) in their study they appealed, that embracement of appropriate leadership style is critical to drive organizational innovation. It is because, the motivational role played by leaders not only induce employs to excel their performance but also asked them to contribute innovatively. With similar direction, another study conducted by Gumusluoğlu and Ilsev (2009) considering 167 Research and Development managers from 65 small and medium enterprises of Turkish software development companies. They reached their final verdict with positive notation, that is, transformational leadership positively influenced on organizational innovation.

They also argued that SMEs practicing transformational leadership show more growth propensity than other SMEs operating in the same industry.

Assertive leadership style, such as transformational leadership, reacts with positive intention and creativity at workplace; some of the actions represent organization vision, autonomy, encouragement and challenges for followers. Therefore, a leader's attitudes towards organization and organizational culture act as enforcing power for creativity and at individual consideration serve as a reward. The effects of transformational leadership on organizational innovation in literature positively associated. Therefore, in accordance with literature, we also predict that there is a positive relationship between transformational leadership and organizational innovation in financial institutions of Bangladesh.

Hypothesis₃: Transformational leadership positively induced organizational innovation

III. Data and methodology of the study

This study based on primary data, which were collected through a structured questionnaire with 5 (five) points Likert's scale. As a sample, we consider public commercial banks those are operating in Dhaka city. In total, 400 surveys were sent to different branches during the data collection period and eventually we received 385 responses from financial institutions. It is mentionable here that prior permission was undertaken from higher authority regarding survey data collection so that respondents can response with ease and the response bias can eliminate to the extent zero. After date cleansing and sorting procedures, we finally confirmed 350 responses were dully filled up with all pertinent information. This indicates the response rate is 75%, simultaneously which also reduce the non-response bias in estimation. Table 1 reports technical details of the research sample.

The study samples are strongly homogeneous in terms of their nature of the operation that is all the sample firms are operating the sample industry namely, bank-based financial institutions. The first reason for selecting as a sample, that it is adequate to investigate both individual – level creativity and at organizational innovation. Second, serving customers with financial services and products requires individual capacity and organizational assistance for gaining customers confidently. The Sample consists of 76% male respondents and 24% female respondents along with 38% sample possess more than 12 years banking job experience, 20% sample possess experiences between 9 -12 years, 39% possess work experience between 3 to 9 years and rest of samples to possess work experience less than 3 years. Considering educational qualification, 9% samples hold a college degree, 30% sample holding graduate's degree from university and 51% samples having a post-graduate degree.

Table 1 Technical details of the research

Category	Remarks
Sector	Bank-based financial institutions
Geographical location	Bangladesh
Methodology	Stricture questionnaire
Procedure	Stratified sampling
Universe population (Branches of Bank)	758
Sample size (response)	350 (48%)
Period of data collection	From July to September 2018

All the questionnaires were transformed into 5 points Likert's scale representing 1 for strongly disagree to 5 for strongly agreed. The higher scale point presence in the response indicates to increase the presence of research variables in the organization. A structured questionnaire, according to Groves et al. (2011). with Likert's scale allows receiving standardized responses from universe sample.

Measures

The Uses constructs in measuring effects for latent variable play an important role in management researcher. Therefore, researchers concentrating on behavioral elements always prefer to use pre-established instruments, which are tests and validated earlier. Given that, construction of new measurement instruments is a time-consuming and complex task. In this study, we also used pre-tested and established construct of observing the latent variable impact on the dependent variable.

Transformational leadership

Leadership refers continuous motivation and encouragement to followers of achieving targeted goal either in individual or in organizational aspects. Leaders in the organization refer as a model for their behavior, attitudes and demonstrated capability in addressing various situations. Among other leadership style, transformational leaders in the organization align individual goal into organizational goal and motive them towards common goal. Transformational leadership including, motivation, stimulation, and encouragement, is inevitable to attain optimal performance, in which knowledge and creation work in such a way for organizational development through increasing organizational performance. The construct for measuring transformational leadership, in this study we used four items developed by McColl-Kennedy and Anderson (2002). This scale is duly appreciated and acknowledge by other researchers of explaining the transformational leadership effects on organizational performance see, for example, (García-Morales et al., 2012; Tims et al., 2011; Kelloway et al., 2012; Fein et al., 2010). This study includes a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to validate the scale of measurement constructs ($\chi^2_2 = 15.10$, NFI=0.958, RFI= 0.874, GFI= 0.974, IFI= 0.963 and CFI=0.963).

Organizational innovation

Innovation is one of the key features adding a competitive position for the organization. Presence of innovativeness in the organization helps to utilized market opportunities with competitive position by offering versatile product and service line with existing one. Organizational innovation plays critical role in enjoying first mover advantages in business process. Rapid innovation allows firm to avail grater benefits and income generation opportunities with isolation from new mechanisms adaption. A group of researchers assesses the effects of organizational innovation by using reliable and validated instruments see, for example (Terjesen et al., 2016; Soto-Acosta et al., 2016; Carter and Tamayo, 2017). In this study, we extracted latent construct developed by Antoncic and Hisrich (2001). We also perform confirmatory factor analysis to validate the used instruments ($\chi^2_2 = 4.62$, NFI=0.989 RFI= 0.966, GFI= 0.974, IFI=

0.993 and CFI=0.993.

Organizational performance

Selection of optimal and standardized measurement scale for organizational performance is the problem itself, therefore, the use of subjective measures in addressing organizational performance well appreciated. According to Deninson and Mishra (2003) used subjective measures rather than objective measures is best fitted ineffectiveness in model estimation. Based on existing literature of measuring organizational performance study used a construct developed by Murray and Kotabe (1999). The use of scales in evaluating performance relative to main competitors is one of the most widely accepted practices in recent studies ((Capar and Kotabe, 2003; Brouthers and Brouthers, 2003; García-Sánchez et al., 2018b; Martín-Rojas et al., 2017). This study includes a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to validate the scale of measurement constructs ($\chi^2_5 = 29.83$, NFI=0.970 RFI= 0.975, GFI= 0.974, IFI= 0.975 and

CFI=0.975).

Figure 1 Conceptual model with a possible hypothesis of the study

IV. Model estimation and analysis

This section represents the preliminary and model estimation of the study. Table 1 exhibits a summary of descriptive statistics and pairwise correlation. The test statistics of pairwise correlation matrix confirmed a positive association between transformational leadership, organizational innovation and organizational performance and the coefficients are statistically significant at a 1% level of significance.

Table 2 Means, standard deviations, consistency indices, and correlation coefficients of the constructs used in the study

	Mean	SE	CA	CR	AVE	1	2	3
Transformational leadership style	3.728	0.44	0.89	0.887	0.67	<i>0.820</i>		
Organizational performance	3.860	0.48	0.76	0.848	0.78	0.540*	<i>0.887</i>	
Organizational innovativeness	3.820	0.49	0.79	0.807	0.72	0.469*	0.495*	<i>0.85</i>

Note: Mean the average score for all of the items included in this measure; CA, Cronbach's α ; CR, composite reliability; AVE, average variance extracted. The numbers in italics on the diagonal are the square root of the average variance extracted. Off-diagonal elements are correlations among constructs

Before hypothesis investigation with structural equation model as proposed in figure 1, we perform confirmatory factor analysis as suggested by Anderson and Gerbing (1988) two-step model estimation. Table 3 exhibits the results of the measurement model. We used AMOS 22 to estimate the model. For ensuring reliability and validity of measurement variables, several diagnostic tests was applied and the test results exhibit in Table 2. Internal consistency of measurement construct was measured by evaluating the computed Cronbach alpha and test statistics confirmed used measurement instruments are reliable for model investigation as all the Cronbach Alpha is greater than the cut-off value 0.70. Construct validity was evaluated by average variance explained in each dimension, obtained by applying confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), it is observed that the coefficients of AVE are higher than 0.50 in all dimension, which confirm the survey instrument validity (Hair et al., 1998). Composite reliability was also investigated by evaluating the composite reliability ratio, as obtained from CAF. It is obvious that the composite reliability ratio is 0.90 (approximate) in all dimensions, which confirms survey instruments

nest. The discernment validity examined, as Fornell and Larcker (1981) postulated that AVE of each construct is greater and the pair-wise correlation lies between the value of square root of AVE. in summary, all the applied test in confirming reliability and validity ensure measurement instruments reliable and valid.

Table 3 Measurement model results

	γ	R^2	CR	AVE	Goodness of fit index
LS1	0.824***(0.321)	0.678			$\chi^2_{62} = 228.83$
LS2	0.963***(0.072)	0.927	0.935	0.785	(p=0.00)
LS3	0.859***(0.262)	0.737			NFI=0.917
LS4	0.893***(0.202)	0.797			RFI= 0.895
OI1	0.986***(0.027)	0.972			GFI= 0.
OI2	0.841***(0.292)	0.707	0.915	0.733	IFI= 0.938
OI3	0.636***(0.595)	0.404			CFI=0.938
OI4	0.923***(0.148)	0.851			TLI=0.922
OP1	0.911***(0.170)	0.829			RMSEA=0.03
OP2	0.971***(0.057)	0.942			
OP3	0.924***(0.146)	0.853	0.971	0.871	
OP4	0.926***(0.142)	0.857			
OP5	0.934***(0.127)	0.872			

Notes: γ , the standardized structural coefficient (Standard error are shown in parentheses); R^2 , reliability; CR, composite reliability; AVE, average variance extracted; *** $p < 0.001$

Table 4 reports the structural model estimation in figure 2. The idea behind to perform structural equation model to investigate both direct and indirect effects from the independent variable to the dependent variable by using AMOS 22. The overall model fit index (see, Table 4, column 5) confirmed best fitted with given all the goodness fit index over the cut-off points in all concerned. The standardized path coefficients of both direct and indirect exhibits positive association with organizational performance and the coefficients are also statistically significant at a 1% level of significance. Focusing, transformational leadership effect on organizational performance in bank-based financial institutions in Bangladesh ($\beta = 0.327$, $P < 0.001$). Study findings coefficient suggests that 1% improvement in transformational leadership will improve organizational performance by 0.327% in future. As predicted in the first hypothesis that is, there is a positive association between transformational leadership style and organizational performance. Furthermore, the effects from transformational leadership style to organizational innovation also exhibits positive ($\beta = 0.964$, $P < 0.001$). It is implying that organizational innovation positively induces organizational innovation such that 1% improvement in organizational innovation can fosters operational innovation by 0.964%. Study finding suggested that transformational leadership style encourages employees in the organization to contribute to organizational development with innovative thoughts and idea in the operation. As expected from existing empirical literature, transformational leadership induced organizational innovation with employee's attitudes transformation, which eventually accelerates innovation.

The relationship between organizational innovation and organizational performance also positively linked as predicted in hypothesis three, that is there is a positive influence from organizational innovation to organizational performance. The coefficient between organizational innovation and organizational performance exhibits positive linkage with statistically significant at a 1% level of significance ($\beta = 0.983$, $P < 0.001$). Study findings suggest that organizational innovation encourage

operational performance for example, 1% development in innovativeness in the organization can accelerate organizational performance by 0.983%.

It is apparent from Path model estimation that is organizational performance will be accelerated through transformational leadership and organizational innovation in either way. However, the magnitude from transformational leadership style is less than organizational innovation on organizational performance. Therefore, one can conclude bank-based financial institutions in Bangladesh should focused on innovativeness in the organization through employee encouragement and effective involvement.

Table 4 Structural equation model results (Direct effects, indirect effects, and Total effects)

Hypothesis	Direct effect	Indirect effect	Total effects	Goodness of model fit
Transformational leadership → Organizational innovation	0.964***	-	0.964***	$X^2_{62} = 228.01$ (p=0.00) NFI=0.917; RFI= 0.895 GFI= 0.983 IFI= 0.938 CFI=0.938 TLI=0.922 RMSEA=0.03 AIC=312.01 PNFI = 0.723 PCFI=0.745
Transformational leadership → Organizational innovation	0.327	0.610	0.937***	
Organizational innovation → Organizational Performance	0.983**	-	0.983***	
Organizational Performance				

V. Discussion and further research direction

The prime motivation of this study is to investigate both direct and indirect effects from transformational leadership and organizational innovation on organizational performance of bank-based financial institutions of Bangladesh. Based on measurement variables in the equation, we purposively formulated three hypothesis with full consideration of existing empirical literatures. First hypothesis that is *there is positive association between transformational leadership and organizational performance*. The second hypothesis that is *organizational innovation positively linked with organizational performance* Third hypothesis focusing on transformational leadership and organizational innovation that is *there is a positive relationship between transformational leadership and organizational innovation*. Study findings convincingly reached a final verdict regarding the organizational performance of financial institutions in Bangladesh positively influenced by transformational leadership style and organizational innovation. Study findings further ascertain organizational innovation can foster with effective practice of leadership style in the organization as well.

Leaders act in the organization ultimately influence followers' perception, attitudes and transform their mind set-up about the individual goal to common goal in accordance with organization mission and vision. Leader role in the organization highlighted as mapping force in a productive task with existing organizational resources and ensure effective optimization. Czarnitzki and Kraft (2004) proposed a causal model for explaining transformational leadership as an important influence on organizational innovation.

To summarized the contribution of this study. First ever-empirical investigation considering bank-based financial institutions in examining the relationship between transformational leadership, organizational innovation and organizational performance even though existing literatures provide reach evidence in this regards. Second, the direct effect from transformational leadership and organizational innovation to organizational performance positively associated. Findings suggest that further

improvement in effecting implementation of existing leadership style and encouragement in organizational innovation will enhance organizational performance. This finding is in the line with Koene et al. (2002), Bushra et al. (2011), Lee et al. (2011), Belias and Koustelios (2014). Third, study also unveiled indirect effect from transformational leadership through mediating organizational innovation positively influence organizational performance as well.

Figure 2 Results of structural equation model

Limitation and Further suggestions

Even though this current research finding exposed interesting insight in explaining the relationship between transformational leadership, organizational innovation and organizational performance of bank-based financial institutions in Bangladesh, are performing in public sector. Apart from that, still there are several inherent limitations also available that is essential to address as a future direction in performing research. First, the research sample concentrated only those banks based financial institutions operating public sector and located in the capital of Bangladesh. It is implying that sample diversification was ignored in this study. Therefore, further study focusing same nexus with sample diversification in sample selection could produce more reliable and convincing findings and allow greater possibility to formulate policy implication in confident way.

Second, financial system of Bangladesh consists of both Bank and non-bank financial institutions however in the study we only focused on bank based financial institutions by ignoring other financial institutions that are operating namely, insurance companies and leasing companies. Since both insurance and leasing maintain a significant financial market share and most importantly they are located in the capital.

Third, study sample consists of only public commercial banks, therefore the findings can only make generalized conclusion not for private commercial banks and for public commercial banks. Diversified sample selection might show different picture regarding the influence of transformational leadership and organizational innovation to organizational performance.

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Reference

- Adjibolosoo S. (2018) A Human Factor Approach to Human Resource Management and Organizational Development. *The Human Factor Approach to Managerial and Organizational Efficiency and Effectiveness*. Springer, 75-96.
- Aguenza BB and Som APM. (2018) Motivational factors of employee retention and engagement in organizations. *IJAME*.
- Al-Omari MAM and Hung DKM. (2012) Transformational leadership and organizational innovation: The moderating effect of emotional intelligence. *International Business Management* 6: 308-316.
- Al Khajeh EH. (2018) Impact of Leadership Styles on Organizational Performance.
- Anderson JC and Gerbing DW. (1988) Structural equation modeling in practice: A review and recommended two-step approach. *Psychological Bulletin* 103: 411.
- Antoncic B and Hisrich RD. (2001) Intrapreneurship: Construct refinement and cross-cultural validation. *Journal of Business Venturing* 16: 495-527.
- Appelbaum SH, Profka E, Depta AM, et al. (2018) Impact of business model change on organizational success. *Industrial and Commercial Training* 50: 41-54.
- Arif S and Akram A. (2018) Transformational Leadership and Organizational Performance. *SEISENSE Journal of Management* 1: 59-75.
- Arslan A and Staub S. (2013) Theory X and theory Y type leadership behavior and its impact on organizational performance: Small business owners in the Şişane Lighting and Chandelier District. *Procedia-social and behavioral sciences* 75: 102-111.
- Avolio BJ and Bass BM. (1995) Individual consideration viewed at multiple levels of analysis: A multi-level framework for examining the diffusion of transformational leadership. *The leadership quarterly* 6: 199-218.
- Avolio BJ, Bass BM and Jung DI. (1999) Re-examining the components of transformational and transactional leadership using the Multifactor Leadership. *Journal of occupational and organizational psychology* 72: 441-462.
- Azar G and Ciabuschi F. (2017) Organizational innovation, technological innovation, and export performance: The effects of innovation radicalness and extensiveness. *International Business Review* 26: 324-336.
- Barling J, Akers A and Beiko D. (2018) The impact of positive and negative intraoperative surgeons' leadership behaviors on surgical team performance. *The American Journal of Surgery* 215: 14-18.
- Bass B and Avolio B. (1995) *MLQ multifactor leadership questionnaire*: Mind Garden.
- Bass BM and Avolio BJ. (1990) *Transformational leadership development: Manual for the multifactor leadership questionnaire*: Consulting Psychologists Press.

- Bass BM and Avolio BJ. (1994) *Improving organizational effectiveness through transformational leadership*: Sage.
- Belias D and Koustelios A. (2014) Transformational leadership and job satisfaction in the banking sector: A review. *International Review of Management and Marketing* 4: 187-200.
- Belliveau P, Griffin A and Somermryer S. The PDMA toolbox for new product development, 2002. John Wiley, New York.
- Bhargavi S and Yaseen A. (2016) Leadership styles and organizational performance. *Strat Manage Q* 4: 87-117.
- Brouthers KD and Brouthers LE. (2003) Why service and manufacturing entry mode choices differ: The influence of transaction cost factors, risk and trust. *Journal of Management Studies* 40: 1179-1204.
- Bushra F, Ahmad U and Naveed A. (2011) Effect of transformational leadership on employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment in banking sector of Lahore (Pakistan). *International Journal of Business and Social Science* 2.
- Calantone RJ, Cavusgil ST and Zhao Y. (2002) Learning orientation, firm innovation capability, and firm performance. *Industrial marketing management* 31: 515-524.
- Capar N and Kotabe M. (2003) The relationship between international diversification and performance in service firms. *Journal of international business studies* 34: 345-355.
- Carter M and Tamayo A. (2017) Entrepreneurial and intrapreneurial skills of managers as determinant of organizational performance of small and medium enterprises in Davao region, Philippines.
- Cohen WM and Levinthal DA. (1990) Absorptive capacity: A new perspective on learning and innovation. *Administrative Science Quarterly* 35: 128-152.
- Czarnitzki D and Kraft K. (2004) Firm leadership and innovative performance: Evidence from seven EU countries. *Small Business Economics* 22: 325-332.
- Day DV and Lord RG. (1988) Executive leadership and organizational performance: Suggestions for a new theory and methodology. *Journal of management* 14: 453-464.
- Elenkov DS. (2002) Effects of leadership on organizational performance in Russian companies. *Journal of Business Research* 55: 467-480.
- Fartash K, Davoudi S, Baklashova T, et al. (2018) The Impact of Technology Acquisition & Exploitation on Organizational Innovation and. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education* 14: 1497-1507.
- Fein EC, Tziner A and Vasiliu C. (2010) Age cohort effects, gender, and Romanian leadership preferences. *Journal of Management Development* 29: 364-376.
- Fornell C and Larcker DF. (1981) Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of marketing research* 18: 39-50.
- Fowler JL and O'Gorman JG. (2005) Mentoring functions: A contemporary view of the perceptions of mentees and mentors. *British journal of management* 16: 51-57.
- García-Morales VJ, Jiménez-Barrionuevo MM and Gutiérrez-Gutiérrez L. (2012) Transformational leadership influence on organizational performance through organizational learning and innovation. *Journal of Business Research* 65: 1040-1050.
- García-Morales VJ, Matias-Reche F and Hurtado-Torres N. (2008) Influence of transformational leadership on organizational innovation and performance depending on the level of organizational learning in the pharmaceutical sector. *Journal of Organizational Change Management* 21: 188-212.
- García-Sánchez E, García-Morales V and Martín-Rojas R. (2018a) Influence of technological assets on organizational performance through absorptive capacity, organizational innovation and internal labour flexibility. *Sustainability* 10: 770.
- García-Sánchez E, García-Morales VJ and Martín-Rojas R. (2018b) Analysis of the influence of the environment, stakeholder integration capability, absorptive capacity, and technological skills on

- organizational performance through corporate entrepreneurship. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal* 14: 345-377.
- García-Morales VJ, Lloréns-Montes FJ and Verdú-Jover AJ. (2008) The effects of transformational leadership on organizational performance through knowledge and innovation. *British journal of management* 19: 299-319.
- Giarratana MS and Torrisi S. (2010) Foreign entry and survival in a knowledge-intensive market: emerging economy countries' international linkages, technology competences, and firm experience. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal* 4: 85-104.
- Gowen CR, Henagan SC and McFadden KL. (2009) Knowledge management as a mediator for the efficacy of transformational leadership and quality management initiatives in US health care. *Health care management review* 34: 129-140.
- Groves RM, Fowler Jr FJ, Couper MP, et al. (2011) *Survey methodology*: John Wiley & Sons.
- Gumusluoğlu L and Ilsev A. (2009) Transformational leadership and organizational innovation: The roles of internal and external support for innovation. *Journal of Product Innovation Management* 26: 264-277.
- Hair J, Anderson R, Tatham R, et al. (1998) *Multivariate data analysis with readings* Prentice-Hall International Inc.
- Harris A, Leithwood K, Day C, et al. (2007) Distributed leadership and organizational change: Reviewing the evidence. *Journal of educational change* 8: 337-347.
- Hoxha A. (2015) Empowerment and Trust as Mediators of the Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Organizational Effectiveness. *European Journal of Economic & Political Studies* 8.
- Hsiao FS and Hsiao M-CW. (2006) FDI, exports, and GDP in East and Southeast Asia—Panel data versus time-series causality analyses. *Journal of Asian Economics* 17: 1082-1106.
- Ismail Al-Alawi A, Yousif Al-Marzooqi N and Fraidoon Mohammed Y. (2007) Organizational culture and knowledge sharing: critical success factors. *Journal of knowledge management* 11: 22-42.
- Jung DD, Wu A and Chow CW. (2008) Towards understanding the direct and indirect effects of CEOs' transformational leadership on firm innovation. *The leadership quarterly* 19: 582-594.
- Jung DI, Chow C and Wu A. (2003) The role of transformational leadership in enhancing organizational innovation: Hypotheses and some preliminary findings. *The leadership quarterly* 14: 525-544.
- Jung DI and Sosik JJ. (2002) Transformational leadership in work groups: The role of empowerment, cohesiveness, and collective-efficacy on perceived group performance. *Small group research* 33: 313-336.
- Kelloway EK, Turner N, Barling J, et al. (2012) Transformational leadership and employee psychological well-being: The mediating role of employee trust in leadership. *Work & Stress* 26: 39-55.
- Koech PM and Namusonge G. (2012) The effect of leadership styles on organizational performance at state corporations in Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Commerce* 2: 1-12.
- Koene BA, Vogelaar AL and Soeters JL. (2002) Leadership effects on organizational climate and financial performance: Local leadership effect in chain organizations. *The leadership quarterly* 13: 193-215.
- Lee PK, Cheng TE, Yeung AC, et al. (2011) An empirical study of transformational leadership, team performance and service quality in retail banks. *Omega* 39: 690-701.
- Lengnick-Hall CA. (1992) Innovation and competitive advantage: What we know and what we need to learn. *Journal of management* 18: 399-429.
- Lieberman MB and Montgomery DB. (1988) First-mover advantages. *Strategic Management Journal* 9: 41-58.
- Makri M and Scandura TA. (2010) Exploring the effects of creative CEO leadership on innovation in high-technology firms. *The leadership quarterly* 21: 75-88.

- Martín-Rojas R, Fernández-Pérez V and García-Sánchez E. (2017) Encouraging organizational performance through the influence of technological distinctive competencies on components of corporate entrepreneurship. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal* 13: 397-426.
- McCull-Kennedy JR and Anderson RD. (2002) Impact of leadership style and emotions on subordinate performance. *The leadership quarterly* 13: 545-559.
- McFadden KL, Henagan SC and Gowen III CR. (2009) The patient safety chain: Transformational leadership's effect on patient safety culture, initiatives, and outcomes. *Journal of Operations Management* 27: 390-404.
- Mokhber M, bin Wan Ismail WK and Vakilbashi A. (2015) Effect of transformational leadership and its components on organizational innovation. *Iranian Journal of Management Studies* 8: 221-241.
- Morecroft JD, Asay D, Sterman JD, et al. (1994) *Modeling for learning organizations*: Productivity, Incorporated.
- Muehlheusser G, Schneemann S, Sliwka D, et al. (2018) The contribution of managers to organizational success: Evidence from German soccer. *Journal of Sports Economics* 19: 786-819.
- Murray JY and Kotabe M. (1999) Sourcing strategies of US service companies: a modified transaction-cost analysis. *Strategic Management Journal* 20: 791-809.
- Naranjo-Valencia JC, Jiménez-Jiménez D and Sanz-Valle R. (2016) Studying the links between organizational culture, innovation, and performance in Spanish companies. *Revista Latinoamericana de Psicología* 48: 30-41.
- Nonaka I and Takeuchi H. (1995) *The knowledge-creating company: How Japanese companies create the dynamics of innovation*: Oxford university press.
- Northouse PG. (2018) *Leadership: Theory and practice*: Sage publications.
- Ogbonna E and Harris LC. (2000) Leadership style, organizational culture and performance: empirical evidence from UK companies. *International Journal of Human Resource Management* 11: 766-788.
- Oke A, Munshi N and Walumbwa FO. (2009) The influence of leadership on innovation processes and activities. *Organizational Dynamics* 38: 64-72.
- Orabi TGA. (2016) The impact of transformational leadership style on organizational performance: Evidence from Jordan. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies* 6: 89-102.
- Peterson RS, Smith DB, Martorana PV, et al. (2003) The impact of chief executive officer personality on top management team dynamics: one mechanism by which leadership affects organizational performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 88: 795.
- Petrou P, Demerouti E and Schaufeli WB. (2018) Crafting the change: The role of employee job crafting behaviors for successful organizational change. *Journal of management* 44: 1766-1792.
- Rodríguez-Ponce E. (2007) Leadership styles, strategic decision making and performance: an empirical study in small and medium-size firms. *Interciencia* 32: 522-528.
- Sivadas E and Dwyer FR. (2000) An examination of organizational factors influencing new product success in internal and alliance-based processes. *Journal of Marketing* 64: 31-49.
- Soto-Acosta P, Popa S and Palacios-Marqués D. (2016) E-business, organizational innovation and firm performance in manufacturing SMEs: an empirical study in Spain. *Technological and Economic Development of Economy* 22: 885-904.
- Strange JM and Mumford MD. (2002) The origins of vision: Charismatic versus ideological leadership. *The leadership quarterly* 13: 343-377.
- Subramony M, Segers J, Chadwick C, et al. (2018) Leadership development practice bundles and organizational performance: The mediating role of human capital and social capital. *Journal of Business Research* 83: 120-129.
- Terjesen S, Hessels J and Li D. (2016) Comparative international entrepreneurship: A review and research agenda. *Journal of management* 42: 299-344.

-
- Tims M, Bakker AB and Xanthopoulou D. (2011) Do transformational leaders enhance their followers' daily work engagement? *The leadership quarterly* 22: 121-131.
- Trmal SA, Bustamam USA and Mohamed ZA. (2015) The Effect Of Transformational Leadership In Achieving High-Performance Workforce That Exceeds Organisational Expectation.
- Tushman M and Nadler D. (1986) Organizing for innovation. *California Management Review* 28: 74-92.
- Uhl-Bien M and Arena M. (2018) Leadership for organizational adaptability: A theoretical synthesis and integrative framework. *The leadership quarterly* 29: 89-104.
- Woodman RW, Sawyer JE and Griffin RW. (1993) Toward a theory of organizational creativity. *Academy of Management Review* 18: 293-321.
- Xu G-y and Wang Z-s. (2008) The impact of transformational leadership style on organizational performance: The intermediary effects of leader-member exchange. *2008 International Conference on Management Science and Engineering 15th Annual Conference Proceedings*. IEEE, 1090-1097.
- Yunis M, Tarhini A and Kassar A. (2018) The role of ICT and innovation in enhancing organizational performance: The catalysing effect of corporate entrepreneurship. *Journal of Business Research* 88: 344-356.
- Zhu W, Newman A, Miao Q, et al. (2013) Revisiting the mediating role of trust in transformational leadership effects: Do different types of trust make a difference? *The leadership quarterly* 24: 94-105.